

TEACHING PRONUNCIATION IN ENGLISH**Abdullayeva Sayyora Pulatovna**

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Annotation

The problem of teaching pronunciation at the initial stage of learning English is one of the most important problems in the methodology of teaching English. Teaching correct English pronunciation is extremely difficult. Without the correct pronunciation, the manifestation of the communicative function of the language is not possible. At the initial stage, it is necessary to teach children to pronounce sounds the way native English speakers do.

Key words

Pronunciation, phonetics, productive, intonation, phoneme, expression, language, mastering, composing.

Teaching phonetics as a productive process requires the student to know the structure of the speech apparatus, which is a difficult methodological task, since at this stage this information is the most difficult for students and requires a lot of time and effort on the part of the teacher and students. Nevertheless, this investment of time and effort pays off if students master this skill at the initial stage on a strictly worked out minimum material that provides a motivational level and a reliable basis for the formation of other speech activities.

So, what affects the correct pronunciation?

- ☒ Articulation
- ☒ intonation
- ☒ Correct pronunciation of vowels and consonants

What to look for when learning pronunciation?

Of course, when learning a foreign language, it is necessary to put the practice of speaking and mastering the basics of grammar in the first place. However, do not forget about phonetics, which gives an understanding of the sound composition of the language, which, like a ladder, can take you to the heights of the English language.

When mastering new sounds that have no analogues in the Russian language, it is necessary to isolate them from the context and work with them (reading syllables, parsing words, composing phrases), repeating them after a native speaker. In order to understand how to pronounce sounds, it is necessary to work with high-quality material.

Working with short stories will help you recreate the atmosphere of the correct sound of the speech that needs to be copied. Remember that the pace of the lesson is very important. You should not dwell on phonetic material for a long time, because this can backfire. However, it is quite important to work at a fast (or constantly increasing) pace, which will help you connect sounds, pronounce large sentences, and work on articulation.

Pay attention to sound reproduction exercises (even if you are watching a movie or listening to a song). Such exercises help to overcome interlingua interference (i.e. the influence of one language on another). The main enemy of a foreign language is the substitution of sounds for similar ones used in the native language. As a result of such a “substitution”, communication may be disrupted, when it is difficult for a foreigner to understand what you want to say (what you mean).

- ❑ What can help with pronunciation?
- ❑ Poetry
- ❑ Proverbs
- ❑ Tongue Twisters

When learning English, due to its special phonetics, it is important in what voice the teacher pronounces words and phrases and what the expression on his face is. Of course, the voice of the teacher should be kind, conducive to communication, and the facial expression should correspond to the tone, which should be intriguing, conspiratorial and trusting, or serious, businesslike, expressing the joy of the meeting, inspiring success. The main thing is that the student, entering into communication in English, does not feel fear for a mistake and strives to realize this or that communicative intention with all the means at his disposal.

It is easiest to master the sounds that coincide in both languages, the most difficult - the sounds that are only similar to the sounds of the native language. The most difficult to assimilate are sounds that have no analogues in their native language. In this case, you have to form completely new skills, teach unusual movements of the tongue, lips, soft palate. Depending on the degree of similarity with the phonemes of the native language, the phonemes of a foreign language are divided into three groups:

The first group is phonemes that coincide in English and native languages: [p], [b], [m], [s], [z], [g], [f], [v], [t], [k], [d], [n], [l], [ʃ], [ʒ], [tʃ], [ʒ].

The second group is phonemes that are similar to the phonemes of the native language, but differ from them in a number of essential features, for example, longitude: [i], [i:], [e], [u:], [u], [], [:], [ə].

The third group is phonemes that have no analogues in the native language: consonants [θ], [ŋ], [], [w], [v], [h]; vowels [ə:], [æ]; diphthongs [ei], [ai], [u], [i], [au].

Depending on the degree of difficulty in mastering the phoneme of the English language, the method of its presentation, the nature and sequence of phonetic exercises are determined.

Rhymes can be used to work out a certain sound in phonetic exercises. For each sound, four or five rhymes are given. This group of rhymes, due to the four to five repetitions of sound, allows children to clearly hear the sound and, when memorized, gives repeated repetition of the sound, for example:

- ☒ Together, together
- ☒ Together every day.
- ☒ Together, together
- ☒ We work and play.

One of the most important tasks of teaching English is the preservation and improvement of pronunciation skills. In a non-linguistic environment, there is a rapid decrease in the achieved level. In practice, exercises are used that prevent forgetting phonetic material. For this purpose, tongue twisters are used in the classroom, and phonetic competitions are organized outside of school hours.

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